

LIMITING EXCHANGE OF ALUMINIUM IONS FROM HYDROGEN CLAYS ON THE ADDITION OF NEUTRAL SALTS*

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Different opinions have been expressed regarding the amount of Al^{+++} ions liberated on the addition of neutral salts to hydrogen clays (Mattson, *Soil Sci.*, 1928, 25, 845; Paver and Marshall, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1934, 53, 750). Estimations are recorded in this note of the amounts of Al displaced from a hydrogen clay sol, Latekujan-F, after each successive leaching with normal solutions of $BaCl_2$ and $CaCl_2$, respectively till no Al in the leachate could be detected with 8-oxyquinoline (Berg, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 369). The residue remaining after leaching with $N-BaCl_2$ in the above manner was converted† into hydrogen clay, repeatedly leached with $N-BaCl_2$, as in the previous case and the amounts of Al were estimated in each leachate. The whole sequence of operations described above was repeated nine times. The results are shown in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Hydrogen clay taken = 100 c.c. Colloid content = 25.2 g/litre.

N-salt solution used for each leaching operation = 125 c.c.

Leaching.	Barium chloride			Calcium chloride		
	Al displaced‡.	pH.	Total acidity‡.	Al displaced‡.	pH.	Total acidity‡.
1st	23.2	3.32	30.0	20.8	3.22	23.2
2nd	1.8	3.74	3.5	1.8	3.77	5.0
3rd	0.4	3.98	1.0	0.45	3.80	2.7
4th	0.1	4.10	0.74	0.18	4.0	0.8
5th	Nil	4.54	0.26	Nil	4.02	0.6
Total	23.4	...	35.5	23.23	...	31.3

*The results have been taken from the annual report for 1941-42 submitted to the Imperial Council of Agricultural Research, India on the working of the "Scheme of Research into the Properties of Colloid Soil Constituents".

†By treatment with $N/50-HCl$.

‡ Results are expressed in m.e. per 100 g. of colloid.

Displaced Al and total acidity both decrease with the progress of leaching till the amount of Al falls below 0.002 mg. per 10 c.c. but that of H⁺ ions remains at about $2.8 \times 10^{-5}N$ with BaCl₂ and $9.6 \times 10^{-5}N$ with CaCl₂. The rapid rate at which the quantity of displaced Al⁺⁺⁺ falls with progressive leaching indicates that there is a limit to the displacement of Al⁺⁺⁺ by Ba⁺⁺ under these conditions. The total amount of Al thus obtained does not, however, represent the maximum amount of exchangeable Al (Table II). Ba⁺⁺ ions displace more Al⁺⁺⁺ and H⁺ ions compared to Ca⁺⁺ ions. This is in agreement with the lyotrope series and the *cation effect is regular* (Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227; Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 589). Comparing results of leaching with BaCl₂ with those with CaCl₂, somewhat greater amounts of Al are found with CaCl₂ in the third to fifth leachates of the two salts and and the *p_H* of the corresponding leachates of CaCl₂ is slightly lower. It appears that more displaceable Al⁺⁺⁺ remains after the first leaching with CaCl₂ and hence more Al⁺⁺⁺ and H⁺ come out in later leachings.

TABLE II

No. of leaching of H⁺ clay with 125 c.c. N-BaCl₂.

Serial No. of treatment of H-clay with* BaCl ₂ .	M. equiv. of displaced Al in leachate (calc. per 100 g. colloid).					Total Al displaced (m.e.) per 100 g.
	1st.	2nd.	3rd.	4th.	5th.	
1st	23.20	1.80	0.40	0.10	Nil	25.50
2nd	8.30	0.25	0.20	Nil	"	8.75
3rd	4.62	0.33	Nil	"	"	4.65
4th	4.60	0.04	"	"	"	4.64
5th	4.53	Nil	"	"	"	4.53
6th	3.20	"	"	"	"	3.20
7th	3.90	"	"	"	"	3.90
8th	3.30	"	"	"	"	3.30
9th	3.40	"	"	"	"	3.40

* Reconversion of the resulting Ba-clay into H-clay followed by leaching.

The amount of Al displaced by BaCl_2 is considerably reduced after the first treatment but Al^{+++} ions continue to be liberated tending to a constant value of about 3.4 m.e. for the first leachate. Mattson (*loc. cit.*) found that as often a soil was rendered unsaturated by treatment with dilute acid and then treated with neutral salt solutions, Al and Fe are brought into solution. Paver and Marshall (*loc. cit.*), on the other hand, conclude from their experiments that there is a limit to the quantity of Al which can be displaced on the addition of a neutral salt. Both Mattson as also Paver and Marshall stopped their leaching experiments before they could get the limiting value and consequently their results show a decrease in the sesquioxide content of the leachate with progressive leaching.

The base exchange capacity* of the original hydrogen clay, Latekujan-F is 31.0 m.e. while that of the hydrogen clay obtained after the ninth treatment has been found to be 31.6 m.e. The fact that the liberated Al ions amount to only 3.4 m.e. out of a total of 31.6 m.e. of cations exchanged indicates that H^+ ions form the major fraction of exchangeable ions present in the hydrogen clay obtained after the cycle of operations. In the original hydrogen clay, however, Al^{+++} ions constituted the main portion.

Further work on this topic is in progress.

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*As determined by Parker's BaAc_2 - NH_4Cl method (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1929, 21, 1030).